

Exploring HIV Status Awareness, Perceived Risk, and Stigmatization in Nigerian Urban Youths

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Abstract

Background: HIV continues to pose a serious global public health threat, with young people remaining particularly at risk. Although HIV testing is essential for effective prevention, treatment, and care—as well as for combating stigma and discrimination—testing uptake among youths remains suboptimal. This study aimed to assess HIV status awareness, perceived risk, and attitudes toward stigmatization among youths in an urban area of Rivers State, Nigeria.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 291 youths aged 15 to 24 years, selected through a multistage sampling approach in an urban local government area of Rivers State. Data were analysed using SPSS version 27.

Results: Of the respondents, 184 (63.2%) were aged 15–19 years, and 171 (58.8%) were male. Over half (159; 54.6%) had never undergone HIV testing and were unaware of their status. Only 87 (29.9%) considered themselves at risk of HIV infection, and 59 (20.3%) believed they were at high risk. Stigmatizing attitudes were prevalent, with 250 (85.9%) expressing negative views toward people living with HIV/AIDS. Additionally, 145 (49.8%) felt that such individuals should have some restrictions on their freedom, while 124 (43.1%) were unwilling to maintain friendships with someone living with AIDS. No statistically significant association was found between socio-demographic variables and stigmatizing attitudes ($p \geq 0.05$).

Conclusion: HIV testing rates and awareness of HIV status among youths in this community remain inadequate. A considerable proportion perceive themselves to be at risk of infection, while stigmatizing attitudes toward individuals living with HIV/AIDS are alarmingly high. There is a pressing need for targeted interventions—such as health education and awareness campaigns—to encourage safer sexual practices, promote routine HIV testing, and address stigma.

Introduction

HIV remains one of the most pressing global public health concerns, having caused the deaths of 40.4 million people and currently affecting an estimated 39 million worldwide [1]. As of 2022, approximately 25.6 million people were living with HIV, with 26% of them residing in the WHO African Region. That same year, 630,000 individuals died due to HIV-related causes, while 1.3 million new infections were recorded globally

[1]. The incidence of HIV continues to rise in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly among young people, who represent over 80% of all cases in the region, despite notable progress in both prevention and treatment [2, 3]. Nigeria, in particular, has the highest rate of HIV prevalence among youths in West and Central Africa, estimated at 3.5% [4]. Young people are especially susceptible to HIV and other sexually transmitted

More Information

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infections (STIs), with 27% of new HIV infections in 2020 occurring among this age group [5, 6].

The Nigeria HIV/AIDS Indicator and Impact Survey (NAIIS) reported a national prevalence of 1.3% among individuals aged 15 to 49 years in 2018 [7]. However, youth-specific data showed that about 40% of HIV cases were found among young people that same year [8]. Rivers State had a reported prevalence rate of 3.8%—significantly above the national average of 1.4% [9]. This rising trend is particularly concerning. Limited knowledge about HIV among young males and females, combined with socio-cultural factors, continues to fuel stigma and discrimination against people living with HIV. If not adequately addressed, these negative attitudes could deter young people from accessing HIV testing or adhering to treatment protocols [10, 11].

HIV testing remains a fundamental aspect of the HIV response—critical for prevention, diagnosis, care, treatment, and reducing discrimination [12]. The U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) recommends regular testing—every three to six months—for sexually active and high-risk youth and young adults (YYA) [13]. Despite this, testing rates remain low among YYA, who are often unaware of their status [14]. A recent systematic review of the uptake of HIV self-testing (HIVST) in Nigeria found that while self-testing is generally well accepted, uptake varies by gender, sexual history, and previous testing experience [15]. Risk perception is also a key factor in reducing HIV vulnerability. Accurate personal assessment of HIV risk is a critical driver of behaviour change and a known determinant in reducing infection rates [16, 17]. In fact, how young individuals perceive their own risk plays a central role in shaping the course of the epidemic [18, 19].

Despite widespread efforts to promote HIV education and prevention, significant gaps remain—especially among the youth. Given the complex socio-cultural context of Rivers State and the growing number of young people, it is imperative to understand the dynamics of HIV awareness, risk perception, and stigma among this population. Accordingly, this study aims to assess the prevalence of HIV testing, awareness of HIV status, perceived risk, and attitudes toward stigma in an urban community in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings from this study are intended to provide insight into the challenges faced by young people and support the design of evidence-based interventions. These would aim to enhance knowledge, promote responsible sexual behaviour, increase testing rates, and reduce stigma—ultimately contributing to improved public health outcomes. The study also holds value for policymakers and researchers in shaping targeted strategies for HIV prevention.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted among youths residing in an urban local government area of Rivers State.

Selection and Description of Participants

The study population consisted of youths aged 15 to 24 years who had lived in the urban community for at least six months. Individuals who were severely ill or unwilling to give informed consent were excluded from the study.

A multistage sampling approach was employed to select participants for the study. Using a list of all urban local government areas (LGAs) in Rivers State as the sampling frame, Port Harcourt LGA was randomly chosen. Within this selected LGA, a ward was also selected through simple random sampling, followed by the random selection of one community within that ward. At the community level, cluster sampling was applied. The starting household was identified by balloting, after which contiguous households to the right were systematically selected until the required sample size was achieved. The sample size of 291 was determined using the standard formula for descriptive cross-sectional studies [20], incorporating prevalence data from prior research. A design effect and a 10% non-response rate were factored into the final calculation.

Study Instrument

The research tool was an interviewer-administered questionnaire adapted from both the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) and the Global AIDS Response Progress Reporting framework [21]. The questionnaire was structured into three sections:

- **Section A:** Socio-demographic information (e.g. age, gender, marital status, education, religion)
- **Section B:** History of HIV testing and disclosure
- **Section C:** Attitudes and stigmatization towards individuals living with HIV/AIDS

To assess stigmatization, respondents were asked to agree or disagree with statements such as:

- “People with AIDS are cursed”
- “I do not want to be friends with someone who has AIDS”
- “A person with AIDS must have done something wrong and deserves to be punished”
- “People with AIDS should expect some restrictions on their freedom”
- “People with HIV should be isolated”
- “It is safe for people who have AIDS to work with children”
- “People with AIDS should be ashamed”

Responses were scored such that those who disagreed with stigmatizing statements received a point (1) for each non-stigmatizing response. A total score of 7 indicated the absence of stigmatizing attitudes.

The questionnaire was pre-tested among youths in a demographically similar community to ensure clarity and reliability. Data collection was carried out over a two-week period by trained field assistants, all of whom were themselves youths. Completed questionnaires were reviewed on-site for accuracy and completeness.

Statistics

Data were initially entered and cleaned using Microsoft Excel, then exported to IBM SPSS Statistics version 27 for statistical analysis. Results were presented in frequency tables. Chi-square (χ^2) tests were used to assess associations between variables, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Clearance

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethics review board of a tertiary institution in Rivers State. Permissions were also obtained from relevant community authorities. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and assent was sought from those under the age of 18.

Results

Table 1 indicates that of the 291 participants surveyed, a majority—184 (63.2%)—were between 15 and 19 years of age. Male respondents comprised 171 (58.8%) of the sample, and most respondents—281 (96.6%)—

were single. In terms of religious affiliation, 278 (95.5%) identified as Christian, with over half (52.6%) identifying as Pentecostal. Regarding educational attainment, only 3 participants (1.0%) had no formal education, while the majority, 207 (71.1%), had completed secondary education.

As detailed in Table 2, over half of the respondents—159 (54.6%)—had never tested for HIV and did not know their HIV status. A total of 87 respondents (29.9%) perceived themselves to be at risk of HIV infection, while only 59 (20.3%) considered themselves at high risk.

According to Table 3, a large proportion of the respondents—250 (85.9%)—exhibited stigmatizing attitudes toward people living with HIV/AIDS. Nearly half, 145 (49.8%), believed that individuals with HIV should face some restrictions on their personal freedom, and 124 (43.1%) indicated they would not want to be friends with someone who has AIDS.

Table 4 examines the relationship between socio-demographic factors and stigma, revealing no statistically significant associations between any socio-demographic characteristics and stigmatizing attitudes ($p \geq 0.05$).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Youths In Rivers State

Variables	Frequency n=291	Percent
Sex		
Male	171	58.8
Female	120	41.2
Age		
15-19	184	63.2
20-24	107	36.8
Religion		
Christian	278	95.5
Moslem	12	4.1
Traditionalist	1	0.3
Denomination		
Catholic	63	21.6
Pentecostal	153	52.6
Protestant	29	10.0
Others	46	15.8
Marital Status		
Single	281	96.6
Married	9	3.1
Living with a partner	1	0.3
Level of Education completed		
No education	3	1.0
Primary	79	27.1
Secondary	207	71.1
Tertiary	2	0.7
Occupation		
Student	239	82.1
Others	52	17.8

Table2: HIV Testing Uptake, Knowledge of HIV Status, Risk Perception among Youths in Rivers State

Variables	Frequency n=291	Percent (%)
Ever tested for HIV + Know HIV Status		
Yes	132	45.4
No	159	54.6
HIV Risk Perception		
Yes	87	29.9
No	204	70.1
Level of HIV Risk		
High	59	20.3
low	232	79.7

Table 3: HIV Stigmatization among Youths in Rivers State

Variables	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)
People who have AIDS are cursed. (n=291)			
Yes	9(3.1)	16(5.5)	25(8.6)
No	162(55.7)	104(35.7)	266(91.4)
People who have AIDS should be ashamed (n=291)			
Yes	54(18.6)	36(12.4)	90(30.9)
No	117(40.2)	84(28.9)	201(69.1)
People with AIDS must expect some restrictions on their freedom. (n=291)			
Yes	102(35.1)	43(14.8)	145(49.8)
No	69(23.7)	77(26.5)	146(50.2)
A person with AIDS must have done something wrong and deserves to be punished. (n=291)			
Yes	15(5.2)	13(4.5)	28(9.6)
No	156(53.6)	107(36.8)	263(90.4)
People who have HIV should be isolated. (n=291)			
Yes	53(18.2)	33(11.3)	86(29.6)
No	118(40.5)	87(29.9)	205(70.4)
I do not want to be friends with someone who has AIDS. (n=288)			
Yes	77(26.7)	47(16.3)	124(43.1)
No	93(32.3)	71(24.7)	164(56.9)
People who have AIDS should not be allowed to work. (n=286)			
Yes	58(20.3)	38(13.3)	96(33.6)
No	109(38.1)	81(28.6)	190(66.4)
HIV Stigmatization (n=291)			
Yes	147(50.5)	103(35.4)	250(85.9)
No	24(8.2)	17(5.9)	41(14.1)

Table 4: Relationship between Socio-Demographic Variables and HIV Stigmatization among Youths in Rivers State

Variables	HIV Stigmatization		Total	X (p)
	Yes (n=250)	No(n=41)		
Age				
15-19	162(55.7)	22(7.6)	184(63.2)	1.881(0.116)
20-24	88(30.2)	19(6.5)	107(36.8)	
Sex				
Male	147(50.5)	24(8.3)	171(58.8)	0.001(0.553)
Female	17(5.8)	103(35.4)	120(41.2)	

Religion				
Christianity	239(82.1)	39(13.5)	278(95.6)	0.231(0.726)
Islam	10(3.4)	2(0.7)*	12(4.1)	
Traditionalist	1(0.3)*	0(0)*	1(0.3)	
Marital status				
Single	243(83.5)	38(13.1)	281(96.6)	2.992(0.244)
Married	6(2.1)	3(1.0)*	9(3.1)	
Cohabiting	1(0.3)*	0(0)*	1(0.3)	
Level of Education completed				
No education	3(1.0)*	0(0)	3(1.0)	1.088(0.864)
Primary	69(23.7)	10(3.4)	79(27.1)	
Secondary	176(60.5)	31(10.7)	207(71.2)	
Tertiary	2(0.7)	0(0)	2(0.7)	

Note: *Fishers Exact

Discussion

This research explored the prevalence of HIV testing, awareness of HIV status, perceived risk, and stigmatization among youth in an urban community in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings indicated that the rates of HIV testing and awareness of HIV status were consistent among the youth in the area, with less than half of the respondents having ever undergone HIV testing or knowing their status. These findings are comparable to those in a Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) conducted among young adults in Nigeria [22]. In contrast, higher proportions were reported in a similar study among rural youth in Rivers State, Nigeria [23], and in the Swaziland HIV Incidence Measurement Survey conducted among young adolescents in Eswatini, a nation with the highest HIV prevalence globally [24]. Overall, HIV testing and awareness were found to be inadequate, which has critical public health implications, potentially leading to delayed diagnoses and increased HIV transmission. There is an urgent need for enhanced public health education and awareness campaigns focused on the importance of HIV testing and promoting responsible sexual behaviour among youth.

Regarding HIV risk perception, one-third of the youth surveyed believed they were at risk of contracting HIV, with a quarter considering themselves at high risk. This suggests that the proportion of those perceiving themselves as at high risk is smaller than those who acknowledged any level of risk. This pattern was similarly observed in rural youth populations in Nigeria [23]. A comparative study between rural and urban youth in Rivers State found that risk perception was higher among those in rural areas than in urban settings [25]. A significantly lower proportion of youth in Borno State reported high-risk perceptions, with only 5 (1.4%) of urban respondents rating themselves as high risk [26].

The finding that a quarter of youth regarded themselves as at high risk for HIV implies that these individuals may be engaging in behaviours that increase their HIV risk, such as unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and substance-influenced sexual activities. Those who perceive themselves as at high risk are also more likely to experience stigmatization, fear, and emotional distress, which could deter them from seeking testing, treatment, or support. Therefore, tailored interventions focusing on health education, enhanced awareness about HIV transmission and prevention, and the availability of counselling and testing services are vital to addressing the health needs of these youth.

Stigmatizing attitudes towards people living with HIV/AIDS were prevalent, with some respondents believing that individuals with HIV should face restrictions on their freedoms or avoid social interaction. This finding aligns with previous studies highlighting widespread HIV stigma in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African countries [23, 27-28]. Such attitudes reflect the influence of societal and cultural norms, negative media portrayals, and peer and family opinions. The stigma surrounding HIV can significantly impact mental health, leading to higher levels of stress, anxiety, and depression among HIV-positive youth. It also hinders social inclusion and affects the general well-being and quality of life for youth living with HIV/AIDS. Thus, interventions promoting education, empathy, positive media representation, and policy reform are necessary to challenge these stigmatizing views.

There was no significant correlation between stigmatization and socio-demographic characteristics such as age, religion, education, or marital status. This suggests that stigma is a widespread issue affecting youth across diverse socio-demographic backgrounds. As such, stigma reduction initiatives should be designed

to target all youth, regardless of their background, and focus on fostering inclusive attitudes such as empathy and respect.

Strength and Limitation of the Study

While the study provided valuable insights into HIV testing uptake, risk perception, and stigmatization among youth, its cross-sectional and descriptive design precludes the ability to establish causality. Additionally, risk perception was measured as a binary variable, warranting cautious interpretation. The cross-sectional nature of the study may have led to underreporting of risk perceptions due to sampling errors, the use of interviewer-administered questionnaires, and social desirability bias. Using self-administered surveys may help mitigate these biases and yield more accurate results regarding sexual behaviour and HIV risk perceptions.

Conclusion

This study investigated HIV testing prevalence, awareness of HIV status, perceived risk, and stigmatizing attitudes among youth in an urban community in Rivers State, Nigeria. It found that fewer than half of the youth had tested for HIV or knew their HIV status. One-third perceived themselves at risk of HIV, and a quarter considered themselves at high risk. Stigmatizing attitudes toward people living with HIV/AIDS were common, with some participants expressing negative views regarding the freedoms of those with HIV. There was no significant relationship between stigma and socio-demographic characteristics.

The lack of HIV status awareness may contribute to delayed diagnoses and increased HIV transmission, underscoring the need for public health education and awareness campaigns. Youth who perceive themselves as high risk may be engaging in behaviours that increase their vulnerability to HIV. The stigmatization of HIV-positive individuals may prevent them from seeking necessary care, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions such as health education, awareness campaigns, counselling, and testing services. Stigma-reduction initiatives should be implemented across all youth groups, promoting inclusive attitudes and providing essential support. We recommend that government and healthcare providers collaborate to create comprehensive stigma-reduction programmes and increase testing services, while policymakers should address the negative societal and cultural attitudes towards discrimination.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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